

Effect of Time on Fiber Optic Cable Characteristics

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Abstract- This study investigates the effect of time on the characteristics of fiber optic cables in the Eastern Region of Saudi Arabia, focusing on degradation metrics such as splice loss, attenuation, and deviation from manufacturer specifications. Utilizing OTDR measurements on 22 live cables of varying ages, the research highlights inconsistencies in degradation patterns, with attenuation losses ranging from 2% to 30%. Environmental factors, undocumented splicing histories, and mixed cable types (e.g., G 652D, G 652C) contributed to data variability. Despite these challenges, the results demonstrate the resilience of fiber optic systems, with some cables exceeding the manufacturer's 25-year lifespan expectation. The study underscores the need for continuous monitoring and standardized documentation to improve long-term performance assessments.

Keywords- Fiber Optics, OTDR, Loss Budget Calculations.

I. INTRODUCTION

Fiber optic cables used as a backbone infrastructure, enables high-speed data transmission critical for both operational efficiency and safety across various facilities. Over time, these cables are exposed to environmental factors and physical stressor that may degrade their performance, potentially impacting overall network reliability. As part of proactive maintenance initiative, this study aims to assess the effects of aging on fiber optic cables using Optical Time Domain Reflectometry (OTDR). OTDR is a widely used method involving a piece of hardware equipment transmitting light paired with a receiver to detect backscatter of light to show a map of the fiber link, which is then sifted with software to characterize the fiber link's geometric features – identifying faults, and measuring signal loss over distance.

This research focuses specifically on analyzing OTDR readings collected from vacant backbone fiber strands within a portion of major network. By examining these strands, we aim to gain valuable insight into how aging affect fiber optic quality and performance, even without active usage. The ultimate objective is to provide data-driven recommendation for enhancing infrastructure longevity and maintenance strategies across the organization.

II. METHODOLOGY

1. Equipment Details

To complete this study, we used the EXFO FTB-2 device. The EXFO FTB-2 is a versatile and high-performance testing platform widely used in fiber optic network analysis. Designed for field applications, it supports a wide range of modules including OTDRs, optical spectrum analyzers and ethernet testing tools making it ideal for

comprehensive network testing and trouble shooting. As of the timing of this study, the device's firmware and software are up to date and is calibrated to perform the necessary tasks.

2. Fiber Cable Specifications

The G652D fiber optic cable is a widely used standard for single mode optical fibers, specified by ITU-T. It is optimized for operation in the 1310 nm wavelength window, with full compatibility in the 1550 nm region, making it suitable for both short and long-distance transmission. G652D features reduced water peak attenuation, enabling efficient wavelength division multiplexing (WDM) across the full spectrum from 1260 nm to 1625 nm. Its low attenuation and dispersion characteristics make it ideal for modern telecommunication networks, including high speed data, voice, and video services.

3. Test Parameters

Wavelength: OTDR tests on G652D fiber are typically conducted at 1310 nm and 1550 nm. 1310 nm is sensitive to splice losses and macro-bends. 1550 nm provides better distance range due to lower attenuation.

Pulse width: pulse width affects the distance and resolution of the test. Short pulses offer high resolution, useful for detecting closely spaced events while longer pulses are used for testing longer fiber spans, providing better dynamic range.

Dynamic Range: Dynamic range is the maximum optical loss an OTDR can measure. For G652D fiber, OTDR with a dynamic range of more than 35dB are typically used to test long haul effectively.

Distance Range: test range is set according to the total length of fiber under test. Test range is slightly longer than the expected fiber length ensures complete trace capture

Test average time: it improves the signal-to-noise ratio. Typically, can set range from 15 seconds to 3 minutes depending on fiber length and required accuracy

Event threshold: it defines the minimum loss level required to register a splice, connector or break. A threshold of 0.1dB -0.2dB is usually appropriate for G652D links

4. Environmental Conditions

The area of operation is located in the Eastern Region in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, which is known of scorching temperatures reaching 52o C in the summer. The results were obtained during the wintertime for convenience. The area is also subject to a barrage of heavy equipment going above the cables during project constructions as well as existing pipelines that generate tremendous heat.

5. Data Gathering

The basis for gathering data is checking every possible 'backbone' fiber optic cable in the supported area of operation where the connection is meant between two communication sites and then utilizing the vacant strands for testing. The testing focuses on 1310nm as it is most susceptible to degradation due to naturally having a higher dB loss coefficient. The overall utilization of each fiber cable is relatively known and well-documented, however, there is a fair number of instances where the cable is spliced to an unknown location. For the sake of simplifying the study, the numbers will be looked upon at face-value and connection details will be ignored.

6. Baseline Formulae

The baseline formula for loss budget calculation is what is currently being used as the industry standard for G 652D OS2 fiber cables as well as the company standard for the number of splices of one splice point every 6 kilometers. Each splice at the time of installation is assumed to have been 0.2 dB as per the company standard. The result-to-baseline comparison shall manifest in x-y charts: one for comparing the percentage of deviation between the average splice loss and the installation splice loss against time, and another for the percentage deviation between average loss coefficient and manufacturer specifications against time – and, finally, one for the percentage deviation between average span loss and loss budget calculation against time.

III. RESULTS

The cables used for gathering the data were 22 in total and are varying in age. For the sake of maintaining confidentiality, their IDs and exact locations are undisclosed. Table 1 showcases the values obtained as well as the deviation percentages. The values compared against the results are obtained from FOA's recommendations.

There are other factors that affected the results. Given that these cables are live, their history regarding splicing into other cables is not well-documented. Therefore, the OTDR results were taken for face-value. Budget Loss was calculated by using the base attenuation of a G 652D cable at 1310 nm of 0.4 dB/km with splice loss of 0.15 dB and connector loss of 0.5 dB. Since splicing depends mainly on the quality of the fusion splicer and technician, there were varying results that led to no correlation. However, attenuation loss of the spans, which was calculated automatically using the built-in OTDR software, showed some degradation among older links – ranging from %2 all the way to %30. Moreover, general loss of the cables also varied from %2 to %20. Another factor to consider was splicing segments of the fiber during outages with other types of cables such as G 652C or even G 656, which has an effect on the properties of the light travelling through the media which may have affected the results.

IV. DISCUSSION

While the results remain inconsistent due to the aforementioned variables, it is still worth noting that there are other aspects of degradations that weren't tested due dealing with live fiber optic cables – such as color-coding degradation; which will affect the overall quality of service during fiber cuts where the technician might take extra returning the service back to normal operation. However, given the marginal difference age makes for fiber optic cable loss, it goes on to show the resilience of fiber optic systems and that they can live beyond the expected lifespan of 25 years by the manufacturer recommendations. Another factor that was not addressed is the effect of light

emission on the properties of the cable with continuous use, which was not tested due to limiting the study on vacant strands that were almost never utilized. Some DWDM equipment have OTDR features that can continuously monitor such effects with the passage of time.

V. CONCLUSION

The findings reveal that fiber optic cables exhibit varying degrees of degradation over time, influenced by environmental conditions, splicing quality, and mixed cable types. While some older cables showed significant deviation in attenuation and splice loss, others performed resiliently, surpassing the typical 25-year lifespan. The study highlights the importance of consistent documentation and advanced monitoring tools, such as DWDM-integrated OTDR, to track long-term performance. Despite inconsistencies, the results affirm the durability of fiber optic systems, suggesting they can remain operational beyond manufacturer expectations. Future research should address unexamined factors like color-coding degradation and continuous light emission effects to further optimize fiber optic network longevity and reliability.

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